

Two New Species for the Genus *Conus*
(GASTROPODA: CONIDAE)

by

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INTRODUCTION

The new taxa being proposed for two *Conus* species, offer a contrast to demonstrate what can be achieved, depending on circumstances under which each is discovered. *Conus halli* was exhaustively researched because Peter Hall, residing in the area, could literally collect specimens right off his front door. Very fortunate indeed, because here is a species with such transfiguring varieties, if collected separately, would inevitably have led to misidentification as being separate species because of the close similarity of at least four such forms to already popularly known species. However, more than sufficient specimens enabled an overall assemblage to show how the varieties took different color or pattern forms, but all progressively merging into one that is typical, incorporating all of the variable features seen individually. However, the similarity observed is evident only at certain formative stages of the varieties. One form resembling *Conus concolor* Sowerby, 1834, for instance, can only be seen when the shell is still in its immature state.

On the other hand, the data on *Conus cernohorskyi*, came from dealer sources, in turn relying on native shell gatherers from different outlying islands in the Philippines. Accurate habit information is invariably meager.

C. cernohorskyi was singled out from among shells for long regarded as another form of the ubiquitous «*magus*». Fortunately, ample study specimens were available for establishing consistency of morphological characteristics and association with varieties of the new species.

Description: Shell stoutly turbinated, solid, with a conic spire consisting of ten flat whorls and a pink obtuse apex, the whorls engraved with strongly prominent spiral threads, the penultimate whorl having a concave slope on subangular shoulders; sides are moderately convex below the shoulder but continuing flat towards the base. The surface of the body whorl is rough to the touch and consists of shallow spiral grooves and ridges crossed with axial striae; some specimens having closely aligned granulations on the spiral ridges. Ground color of the shell is white, with irregular speckles of brown marking the spire in a radial pattern; body whorl is decorated with longitudinal streaks, some of chocolate-brown, others, reddish-brown, and separated into two sections by a median white belt, some specimens having the perpendicular streaks coalescing into merging patches of brown to form partially circular bands. Thickness of the shell is noticeably revealed within the aperture, which is porcelaneous-white and widens somewhat towards the anterior end. Base of the columella has a pronounced twist.

Holotype: The holotype, Figs. 10 & 13, measures 46.4mm×26.8mm and is deposited with the Museum d'Histoire Naturelle, Genova under MHN No. 983.110.

Paratypes: Three paratypes are also lodged with the Museum d'Histoire Naturelle, Genova: Fig. 11 Paratype No. 1, 60.1mm×30mm under MHN No. 983.111.

Fig. 9 Paratype No. 2, 39.5mm×22.1mm under MHN No. 983.112.

Fig. 12 Paratype No. 3, 35.5mm×20.5mm under MHN No. 983.113.

The following additional paratypes are retained for subsequent distribution to other museums:

No. 4 — 55.3mm×32.1mm No. 5 — 54 mm×31.2mm

No. 6 — 55.8mm× 29.6mm No. 7 — 46.6mm×36.6mm

No. 8 — 47.5mm× 25.8mm No. 9 — 45 mm×25 mm

No. 10 — 46.6mm× 26.1mm No. 11 — 41.3mm×22 mm

No. 12 — 46.5mm× 26 mm No. 13 — 40.6mm×23 mm

No. 14 — 40 mm× 22 mm No. 15 — 37 mm×21.7mm

No. 16 — 44.3mm× 25 mm No. 17 — 43 mm×25.3mm

Type locality: Taken by native divers in shallow waters in the vicinity of Borogon, Samar Oriental, Philippines.

Distribution: Known only from the type locality, although occurrence in other Philippine islands is not excluded, but so far not seen outside Philippine waters.

Discussion: The stocky appearance of the new species brings to mind *Conus zeylanicus* Gmelin, 1791 and *Conus stercusmuscarum* Linne, 1758 for similarity of contour, but not of color or pattern, which it resembles *Conus circae* Sowerby, 1858 the closest. Some young specimens of *Conus characteristicus* Fischer, 1807 have a similar squat appearance with rounded shoulders. Immature specimens of the new species, when colored reddish-brown, and patterned with two broad bands can occasionally be confused with *Conus raphanus* Hwass in Bruguiere, 1792, especially when the bulging shoulders of the latter have not yet maturely developed. *Conus cernohorskyi* attains maturity at an average of approximately 46mm in length, but can increase its size exceptionally as demonstrated by Paratype No. 1 at 60.1mm. This is however quite rare.

Etymology: I dedicate the shell to Walter O. Cernohorsky whose voluminous contributions to malacology are familiar to most, and to whom I remain indebted for constant guidance and encouragement in my own research work.

Conus halli sp. nov. da Motta, 1983

Description: Shell smooth, light weight; apex with several post-nuclear whorls obsoletely beaded; spire convexly conic, the spire whorls flat, each having about six fine spiral threads progressively becoming more pronounced and revolving around channeled sutures; shoulder subangulate, with a concave slope, but rounded at its edge, with sides perceptively convex at the top, gradually tapering straight to the base, which is sculptured with a series of raised spiral striae. Coloration is highly variable as are the different pattern decorations; but typically *Conus halli* has a light brownish-white ground color. The apex is pinkish-brown with an area of light brown forming an encircling crest around it; the spire whorls ornamented with lunulate chestnut-brown flames in a radial pattern, which continue to flow onto the body whorl in linear streaks from shoulder to base in alternate stripes of brown and white except where a median white band cuts in two some of the brown streaky decorations; the brown stripes having, barely visible, continuous rows of transverse lines of a darker brown color not seen on the white sections. Aperture is porcelaneous

bluish-white with a narrow border of chestnut brown on the outer lip, which is delicately trenchant; base of columella having a weak spiral twist and white in color. The new species has a moderately thick, dark brown periostracum, barely translucent, except to faintly reveal areas which are white beneath and having some fifteen rows of encircling, evenly spaced tufts. Its operculum is on the small side and shaped like a halfmoon.

The sole of the animal's foot is the color of smoked glass with fine longitudinal etchings; the foot, slightly fleshier and mottled in places; the upper foot tapers off into a dull whitish body; proboscis is flesh-colored with hairline bands; the eye stalks, pale amber darkening towards the tip; siphon under-side being white, the upper, progressively darkening almost to black towards the tip.

Type locality: Pasir Putih, about 180 kilometers east of Surabaya, Java, Indonesia.

Habitat: Specimens have been collected from patches of coral rubble flushed by fresh water from nearby streams and almost devoid of vegetation except for occasional eel-grass, within a stretch of 27 kilometers of mangrove and coral shore-line of sandy-mud. Also found in the vicinity are: *Conus suggilatus* Reeve, *C. magus* Linnaeus, *C. cinereus* Hwass in Bruguiere, *C. suratensis* Hwass, *Cypraea miliaris* Gmelin, *Phalium areola* Linnaeus, and in much abundance, *Strombus canarium* Linnaeus.

Distribution: To date known only from the type locality.

Type specimens: The holotype and six paratypes are deposited with the Museum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneva details of which are described hereunder with registration numbers.

Holotype: (Fig. 2 & 6) measuring 52.8mm×27.8mm is recorded as MHN No. 983.103.

Paratype No. 1: (Fig. 5) measuring 53.6mm×29.6mm with the alternating brow-and-white longitudinal streaks uninterrupted by any center band. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety A and recorded as MHN No. 983.104.

Paratype No. 2: (Fig. 3) measuring 46.5mm×24.8mm and instead of the alternating brown-and-whitet streaks, the ground color is a solid-colored chestnut brown with continuous spiral lines of dark brown

from shoulder to base with a median tessellated band of dark and light brown. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety B and recorded as MHN No. 983.105.

Paratype No. 3: (Fig. 8) measuring 38mm×20.2mm, which is solid dark brown color with some transverse spiral lines barely visible. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety C and recorded as MHN No. 983.106.

Paratype: No. 4: (Fig. 4) measuring 40.3mm×20.7mm which is devoid of any streaky ornamentation, the spire and body whorl being of a solid greyish-brown color with a well defined band of a whitish coloration beneath the shoulder and another at mid-body. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety D and recorded as MHN No. 983.107.

Paratype No. 5: (Fig. 7) measuring 46.2mm×25.6mm is another form with a solid cafe-au-lait ground color with spiral darker lines below the shoulder and at the basal end, divided in the center by a tessellated band of white-and-brown with the brown sections superimposed with rows of short brown dashes, as if portions of the spiral lines have been erased wherever white is seen. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety E and recorded as No. 983.108.

Paratype No. 6: (Fig. 1) measuring 52mm×29mm and is a remarkable departure from the pattern or color of the other varieties. Ground color is solid golden yellow with a white band on the shoulder, mid-section and basal end. This form is designated *Conus halli*, Variety F and recorded as MHN no. 983.109.

The following additional paratypes are retained for subsequent distribution to other museums:

Paratype No. 7 49.8mm×26.4mm
No. 8 50.3mm×26 mm
No. 9 50 mm×26.6mm
No. 10 53.3mm×29.3mm
No. 11 52 mm×26.5mm
No. 12 52.3mm×28.2mm
No. 13 49.9mm×26.1mm
No. 14 51.5mm×28.1mm
No. 15 47.4mm×27.3mm
No. 16 49 mm× 26mm
No. 17 43.6mm×24.2mm

No. 18	40.7mm × 21.6mm
No. 19	46 mm × 25.1mm
No. 20	44 mm × 23.5mm
No. 21	47.6mm × 26.1mm
No. 22	50.6mm × 26.7mm
No. 23	45.4mm × 24.7mm
No. 24	51.6mm × 28 mm

Discussion: Rarely has a *Conus* species been seen within one population varying with such a diversity of ornamentation. The six varieties have been singled out for demonstration of its versatility of patterns, but others, if shown, could provide a close connecting link of intermediates to form an unbroken chain binding all the varieties together as a single species. The specimen selected as holotype incorporates most of the features of all the other individual varieties. *Conus halli* has the closest similarity to *Conus hyaena* Hwass in Bruguiere, 1792 as specifically seen in Var. A (Paratype No. 1) with its linear streaks without the center band. *Conus hyaena* is different because its shoulder is more swollen and the sides constrict acutely to form the impression of a triangle. Var. F (Paratype No. 6) if without the three white bands, would also resemble the golden-yellow form of *hyaena*, except that the latter rarely attains such a large size. Var. C (Paratype No. 3) evokes the image *Conus concolor* Sowerby, 1834 except that it has very slight convexity at the shoulder level by comparison, and its solid color does not have the faintly visible transverse lines marking *Conus halli*. Var. D (Paratype No. 4), if examined individually, could readily be mistaken for *Conus gilvus* Reeve, 1849 from its standard ornamentation. However, it has a more angulate shoulder with flatter sides, and lacks the white shoulder band of *Conus halli*. Collectively, none of the three look-alikes has the circular patch around its apex, a distinct feature of *Conus halli*. *Conus hyaena*, is a species found in Indonesia, the Andaman and China Seas; *Conus concolor* ranges from Papua, New Guinea to the Solomons and *Conus gilvus* has its habitat in the Solomons which extends to the N. E. Australian coast.

Etymology: Named for Peter Hall, who has furnished all the field data and ample specimens making possible its study and the positive identification to establish the status of the new species.

Postscript: Reproduction of radula was not completed in time for inclusion in this paper, but will be published separately.

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RESUMO

O autor propõe 2 novas *taxa* para a família *Conidae* (Mollusca: Gastropoda).

Trata-se de duas novas espécies, uma das Filipinas, outra de Java.

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| 1. | <i>Conus halli</i> | sp. nov. | | | — Paratype No. 6 |
| 2. | » | » | » | » | — Holotype |
| 3. | » | » | » | » | — Paratype No. 2 |
| 4. | » | » | » | » | — Paratype No. 4 |
| 5. | » | » | » | » | — Paratype No. 1 |
| 6. | » | » | » | » | — Holotype |
| 7. | » | » | » | » | — Paratype No. 5 |
| 8. | » | » | » | » | — Paratype No. 3 |
| 9. | <i>Conus cernohorskyi</i> | sp. nov. | | | — Paratype No. 2 |
| 10. | » | | » | » | — Holotype |
| 11. | » | | » | » | — Paratype No. 1 |
| 12. | » | | » | » | — Paratype No. 3 |
| 13. | » | | » | » | — Holotype |

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